

The infrared spectrum of the cycloadduct showed bands at 1680 cm^{-1} ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$). NMR spectrum in CDCl_3 of the cycloadduct (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) showed six methoxy protons at 6.1τ , 13 aromatic protons at 2.7τ and one proton on the C_5 of the oxadiazoline ring at 2.1τ . Such a low field shift of C_5 proton supported structure Ia rather than Ib in which proton is deshielded only by a nitrogen atom.

These 1,2,4-oxadiazolines (1 to 5) were tested for their antifungal activity against *Puccinia striiformis*, *Puccinia recondita*, *Alternaria triticina*, *Alternaria tenuis* and *Pestalotia psidii* by employing standard method of spore germination inhibition. Three concentrations, viz., 1000, 500 and 250 ppm of each of the compounds, have been tried against all the test fungi. All the compounds possessed promising antifungal activity against the above fungi and caused 100% spore germination inhibition even at 250 ppm. The study at still lower concentration is in progress. These observations confirmed our earlier results that presence of methoxy phenyl ring in a compound helps in increasing its activity¹.

Experimental

1,2,4-Oxadiazoline (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$): 3,4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde (2.41 g; 0.01 mole) was dissolved in ether (100 ml) and cooled in an ice bath to 0° . Benzhydroxamoyl chloride (1.1 g; 0.01 mole) in ether (20 ml) was then added with constant shaking and the contents were kept at 0° for some time. Triethylamine (1.2 ml) in ether (20 ml) was then added at a very slow rate with continuous shaking. When the addition was complete the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 0° for 2 hr. The ether layer was separated out and the residue was washed thrice with dry ether. The combined ether layer and the washings on evaporation of the solvent yielded crystalline solid which on recrystallization from benzene-petroleum ether mixture gave fine shining crystals, m.p. 65° (yield 85%).

Testing of the compounds against fungus: Three concentrations (250, 500 and 1000 ppm) of I ($\text{R}=\text{H}$) were taken and treated against fungus *Puccinia striiformis*. The treated spores were incubated for 18 hr and percent spore germination inhibition was calculated by counting 200 spores of each treatment. Spores incubated in water + respective solvent in which the compound is dissolved were used as control. The following

formula is used to calculate % spore germination inhibition.

$$\% \text{ Spore germination inhibition} = \frac{\text{Spore germination inhibition} - \text{Control}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Similarly, other 1,2,4-oxadiazolines were tested for their antifungal activity against *Puccinia striiformis* and other fungi viz., *Puccinia recondita*, *Alternaria triticina*, *Alternaria tenuis* and *Pestalotia psidii*.

References

1. M. RAI, B. KAUR and B. S. DHIR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 416.
2. M. RAI, B. S. DHIR and P. S. KALSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 901.
3. N. SINGH, J. S. SANDHU and S. MOHAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, **42**, 4455.
4. H. WIRLAND, *Chem. Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 1671.

Chemical Examination of *Medicago sativa* Seeds

S. P. SHRIVASTAVA* and S. S. NIGAM

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar-470 008
 Manuscript received 17 September 1981, revised 27 April 1982,
 accepted 8 July 1982

MEDICAGO sativa¹⁻³ (Leguminosae), known as alfalfa or lucerne, is an erect, much branched annual herb. Its seeds are yellowish brown in colour, kidney shaped, rich in vitamin and enzyme. Looking to its nutritive value, it was thought interesting to investigate fixed oil and unsaponifiable matter from the seeds of this plant.

The crushed seeds of *Medicago sativa* were exhaustively extracted with pet. ether ($60-80^\circ$) and a yellowish brown coloured fixed oil (yield 8.50%) was obtained. The oil was found to have following physico-chemical values.

Specific gravity (25°)	...	0.9275
Refractive index	...	1.4624
Acid value	...	5.32
Saponification value	...	178.56
Iodine value	...	8.26
Acetyl value	...	99.50

100 g of the oil was saponified⁴ and the mixed acids (88 g) obtained. The mixed acids were resolved into saturated (7.5 g) and unsaturated (41.5 g) fractions.

Paper and thin layer chromatographic studies showed the presence of palmitic, oleic, linoleic, linolenic and stearic acids.

The fatty acid methyl esters were analysed by gas liquid chromatography using a column of Rheoplex 400-15% supported by chrom-W acid

* Author for correspondence.

washed of S.S. 4.5' X1/B.O.D. maintained at 180°. Injection port and detector block were maintained at 270° with a flow rate of 40 ml/min with a chart speed of 15 mm/min.

The percentage composition of the acids were calculated based on peak areas⁵ and it was found to be composed of palmitic (18.10%), oleic (17.60%), linoleic (60.60%), linolenic (2.20%) and small amount of stearic acids.

Chromatographic resolution of the unsaponifiable matter resulted in the isolation of β -amyrin, m.p. 197-98° and β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-37° which were identified by direct comparison with authentic samples.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S. P. S.) is grateful to Prof. S. S. Nigam for providing authentic samples of β -amyrin and β -sitosterol.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, I. O. CHOPRA and B. S. VARMA, "Supplement to Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Publication and Information Directorate, Hill Side Road, New Delhi, 1969, p. 66.
2. "The Wealth of India, A Dictionary of Indian Raw Material and Industrial products", 1962, IV, 40.
3. W. H. C. D. DE, "Plants of World, the Higher Plants", 1968, Vol. 1, p. 313.
4. T. P. HILDITCH, "The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", Chapman Hall, 1956, p. 574.
5. H. M. Mc NAIR and E. J. BANOLLI, "Basic Gas Chromatography", Berkeley, California, 5th Edn., 1969, p. 139.

Chemical Constituents of *Cephalotaxus griffithii*

MOHD. KAMIL, NOOR AHMAD KHAN, IQBAL AHMAD,
MOHD. ILYAS and WASIUR RAHMAN

Department of Chemistry, A. M. U., Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 31 December 1981, accepted 8 July 1982

CEPHALOTAXUS griffithii HK (Fam. Cephalotaxaceae), collected from Nainital, has been investigated for its chemical constituents and led to the isolation of amentoflavone, sequoiaflavone, apigenin, ginkgetin, mono-O-methyl-C-methyl amentoflavone and quercitrin. 1,6-C-Methyl-1,7-O-methyl amentoflavone constitutes the second report of isolation and characterization of naturally occurring C-methyl biflavones.

Finely ground dried leaves of *Cephalotaxus griffithii* (3 kg) were successively extracted with petrol (40-60°), benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate and finally with acetone. The last two extracts were concentrated and chromatographed over silicagel to furnish six bands labelled as CGI, CGII,

CGIII, CGIV, CGV and CGVI, in order of increasing R_f values. All these bands were separated by preparative tlc (BPF, 36:9:5)² and eluted by acetone mixed with pyridine (2%). CGI (0.2 g) obtained, gave a single spot on tlc, R_f 0.18, m.p. 320°. The yellow solid mass (80 mg) was methylated to give hexa-O-methyl amentoflavone (50 mg), m.p. 173-74°, R_f 0.40. Acetylation (Ac_2O /pyridine) of yellow solid (80 mg) yielded a white solid which crystallized from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH to give amentoflavone hexaacetate, m.p. 242-43°.

The identity of sequoiaflavone and apigenin was established by direct comparison of their acetate and methylethers with those of authentic samples. (m.p., m.m.p., fluorescence in uv light and nmr data).

CGIV, m.p. 350° (decomp), $C_{30}H_{16}O_8(OMe)_2$, λ_{max} (ethanol): 271 nm band I, 335 nm band II. Tetraacetyl derivative, $C_{30}H_{12}O_4(OMe)_4(OAc)_4$, was prepared, m.p., 265-267°. λ_{max} (ethanol): 211, 248-258, 317 nm, finally confirmed as dimethyl ether of amentoflavone (ginkgetin) by comparison with an authentic sample.

CGV, m.p. above 338°, R_f 0.39, $C_{32}H_{22}O_{10}$, M^+566 . Mass spectrum of its methylether showed mol. ion peak at M^+636 and base peak at m/e 621, m.p. 234, R_f 0.45. The compound was finally established as 1,6-C-methyl-1,7-O-methyl amentoflavone by comparison (co.tlc, uv, nmr and mass) with authentic sample³.

CGVI, $C_{31}H_{20}O_{11}$, λ_{max} 275, 352 m μ was hydrolysed (10% HCl) and aglycone and sugar were chromatographed with authentic samples. The sugar was found to be rhamnose. The aglycone, m.p. 182-185° was identical in all respects with quercetin. The structure of CGVI was finally confirmed as quercetin 3-rhamnoside by comparison of its nmr spectral data with that of authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor N. Kawano of Nagasaki University, Nagasaki, Japan and Prof. Dr. H. Wagner of Institut fur Pharmazent Arznei-mittellehre, West Germany for spectral studies. Their thanks are also due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi and U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of research fellowships to two of them (N. A. K. and I. A.).

References

1. K. K. CHEXAL, B. K. HANDA and W. RAHMAN, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1970, 48, 484.
2. M. AQUIL and W. RAHMAN, *J. C. S. Perkin I*, 1981, 1989.